

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL DYNAMIC ANALYSIS FOR A CFRP FORMULA SAE IMPACT ATTENUATOR

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Keywords: *Composite material, CFRP, crashworthiness, axial compression*

1 Introduction

In the last decade crashworthiness has become a fundamental aspect and affects heavily the design of racing cars of all categories. The regulations have become increasingly stringent and restrictive over time and cover different safety related aspects. As a consequence new structures for energy absorption has become indispensable parts for all the high performance cars. The design of these structures has been further complicated by the advent of composite materials which, while having excellent energy absorption capacity, exhibit fully orthotropic behaviour and multiple failure modes and for this reason are quite difficult to predict [1].

Crash investigations on composite structures reported in the literature are mainly based on experimental test analysis of small plates submitted to bending impact and on simple bars, of circular or rectangular cross section, of prismatic or tapered shape, submitted to axial impact [2–6]. Furthermore, some studies can be found concerning composite crash-boxes for automotive applications, but they are still few and do not cover all aspects of composite structure modelling [7-11].

The present paper is dealing with the lightweight design and the crashworthiness analysis of a composite nose cone as the Formula SAE racing car front impact attenuator (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Politecnico di Torino racing car – year 2008

The geometry of a crash-box for racing car application is often very similar to a square frusta. The behaviour of these structures during axial loading conditions is critical to the energy absorption and crushing strength. Square frusta have been observed to fail in four major modes, depending on structural dimensions, material properties and testing conditions: deformation confined at impact wall (Mode-I), longitudinal crack progression (Mode-II), centrally confined circumference crack (Mode III) and large hinge progressive folding (Mode IV). An impact attenuator is designed to produce a Mode-I failure mechanism as the structure maintains a nearly constant crushing strength throughout the crushing process and the highest energy absorption. In order to obtain a progressive crushing from a composite structure during dynamic impact, it is necessary to take into account the lamination process and the gradual smoothing of the wall thickness, avoiding so sudden failure and high peaks of deceleration. A different production process can, in fact, influence significantly the final deformation of the impact attenuator while energy absorption values are not coincident.

The analyzed impact attenuator is manufactured by lamination of prepreg sheets in carbon fibres and epoxy matrix, particularly used for sporting applications.

To reduce the development and testing costs of a new safety design, it is recommendable to use computational crash simulations for early evaluation of safety behaviour under vehicle impact test. Without a doubt, the validation of numerical models for accurate simulation of structural response to crash impacts is an important aspect of crashworthiness research. Indeed, they constitute the necessary tools for the designer to study the

response of the specific structures to dynamic crash loads, to predict global response to impact, to estimate probability of injury and to evaluate numerous crash scenarios, not economically feasible with full scale crash testing [13,14]. The analysis of the crash behaviour was therefore conducted both numerically, using explicit FE codes as LS-DYNA, and experimentally, by means of an appropriately instrumented drop weight test machine.

In order to assess the quality of the simulation results, initially a complete comparative analysis with material characterization was developed on simple CFRP composite tubes subjected to dynamic axial impact loading. The crushing behaviour of these structures was investigated using both shell and solid elements with cohesive material, in order to reproduce also the delamination phenomenon.

Only after having obtained a good correspondence between numerical and experimental results on simple geometry, it is possible to conduct the dynamic analysis on the impact attenuator which presents a more complex geometry.

The explicit code was able to predict experimental results regarding both crash behaviour and absorbing mechanism of the CFRP impact attenuator structure. Force versus displacement diagrams confirm that experimental and numerical results are almost the same. Thus confirms the quality of the used methodology and approach for the design of racing car impact attenuator.

2 Definition of energy absorbing structures

The composite material used in this study is carbon fibre in epoxy resin [10]. The orientation and weave patterns of fibres in a composite component are of great importance to the laminate properties. For the analysed structures a plain weave prepreg, as standard practice in racing applications, was chosen. Composite laminates were formed by hand lay up of the pre-impregnated layers and autoclave curing at 135°C and 7 bar applied pressure. Mechanical testing for material characterization was carried out on an electromechanical Zwick Z100 machine at Politecnico di Torino laboratory. Tensile, interlaminar and relevant fracture mechanic characteristics were evaluated using industry standard techniques. In particular for interlaminar fracture mechanic characteristics the Double Cantilever Bending (DCB) and the Four Point End

Notched Flexure (4ENF) procedures have been utilised.

The mechanical properties for the considered material are reported in Table 1.

Density	1.45 * 10 ⁻³ g/mm ³
Longitudinal Young modulus	53.6 GPa
Transverse Young modulus	55.2 GPa
Poisson's ratio	0.042
Shear modulus ₁₂	2.85 GPa
Shear modulus ₂₃	1.425 GPa
Shear modulus ₃₁	2.85 GPa
Longitudinal tensile strength	0.618 GPa
Transverse tensile strength	0.652 GPa
Longitudinal compressive strength	0.642 GPa
Transverse compressive strength	0.556 GPa
Compressive strength in direction 12	0.084 GPa
In plane shear strength	0.084 GPa
Energy release rate for mode I	0.5 N/mm
Energy release rate for mode II	0.7 N/mm

Table 1. Material properties of the composite layer

After the characterization of the material and before the production of a frontal impact attenuator for a Formula SAE car, it is necessary to reproduce as close as possible the brittle deformation of simple cylindrical tubes, 200 mm long with different wall thickness and radius values, made of the same material. For this target, dynamic numerical analyses using the non-linear LS-DYNA code were conducted, using both shell and solid elements configurations. This latter is intended to capture also delamination and fronding. The quality of the numerical simulation results was checked through their comparison with specific experimental test results, paying particular attention to the capability to reproduce the physical phenomenon.

Only after having properly set the material model properties, a more complex geometry can be modelled. The frontal impact attenuator geometry, resulting from having to fit within the existing envelope dictated by aerodynamic and mechanical constraints and fulfil the technical regulation [15], is essentially a truncated pyramid, having the minor base nearly parallel to the major one (Figure 2).

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL DYNAMIC ANALYSIS FOR A CFRP FORMULA SAE IMPACT ATTENUATOR

Fig. 2. Geometrical configuration of the impact attenuator

The bases have almost rectangular sections with rounded edges to avoid stress concentrations during crushing. The design of the impact attenuator was completed with a trigger which consists in a progressive reduction of the wall thickness, in order to reduce the resisting section locally. This trigger has a double target: reduce the force peak value and initialize structure collapse in a stable way. In particular, three different wall thickness zones were implemented, as shown in Figure 2. The first zone has a laminate thickness of 1.68mm, the second one of 2.16mm and the third one of 2.4mm.

Manufacturing process of impact attenuator initiated with proper definition of mould, obtained from epoxy resin block. In order to get accurate dimensions and good surface finish, mould was produced with environmentally conditioned CNC milling machine. To be more economical and reliable in preparation of attenuator, special attention was given to selection of appropriate mould material that can be reused. Dimensional stability at high temperature and chemical compatibility with attenuator material were some of the main factors to choose epoxy resin block as a mould. To achieve high grade surface finish, the mould were cleaned with Chem Cleaner after machining process in order

to remove all traces of solvent-soluble contaminants such as waxes, silicones, oils, etc. Then after, Chemlease® MPP 712 EZ which acts as a sealant, was used to coat the surface of moulds and cured for about 3 hours at room temperature. After the mould was cured, Chemlease® mould release was applied to remove the finished products from the mould without problem. To avoid voids and entrapped air inside wet prepreg, the mould with laminated attenuator was covered with vacuum plastic bag and subjected to vacuum pressure of 0.98 bar. Then the impact attenuators were transferred to autoclave to apply appropriate controlled pressure and temperature with desired curing cycle. Finally, they were taken out from the autoclave and exposed to room temperature for some times until moulds' temperature gets down to the surrounding temperature. With appropriate tools, the final products were extracted from mould and ready for test. In Figures 3(a) and 3(b) the empty epoxy resin mould and the mould with impact attenuator lay-up prepared for autoclave processing are shown.

Fig. 3. Epoxy resin mould (a) and mould with impact attenuator lay-up (b)

The attention is put on lamination process of the impact attenuator. In particular, two manufacturing cases were considered: lamination without planned overlapped prepreg zones and the improved manufacturing process with intention to avoid overlap at corner edges in order to increase the structural stiffness. The second one is shown in Figure 4.

Laminate overlapping distant from corner edges

Fig. 4. Lamination process of impact attenuator

3 Numerical modelling

Before manufacturing and testing the cylindrical specimens and the impact attenuator, FE analyses were performed using the commercial solver LS-DYNA.

The tubes were modelled with two different modes: with shell elements and with solid ones (Figure 5).

Fig. 5. Tube modeled with a) shell and b) solid elements

In the first case only the middle surface of the tube was modelled using a multi-layered shell property with *PART_COMPOSITE. According to this card, the laminate has a thickness defined as the sum of each individual layer. Laminate theory was also activated with LAMSHT parameter in *CONTROL_SHELL card, to correct for the assumption of a uniform constant shear strain through the thickness of the shell. For the second case, instead, the tube was completely modelled, separating the external laminate from the internal one through a cohesive material layer. Experimental observations show that the amount of fibres bending inside the cylindrical tube radius is equal to the outside ones [16]. For this reason the cohesive zone was modelled in the middle of the tube thickness. Particular attention was given to the material definition of composites. MAT_54 was used, that implement the Chang-Chang criteria, thanks to its

ability to give a numerical behaviour comparable to experimental one [9]. A moving rigid wall planar with a finite mass of 294 kg and an initial velocity of about 4 m/s represents the impacting mass. Moreover a self-contact was defined on the tube surfaces, in order to avoid element penetration during crushing. As regard the boundary conditions, the nodes at the bottom are constrained in all degrees of freedom in order to represent the real fixture. Table 2 reports the main numerical results for the two considered configurations, for what concerns the final crushing stroke and the average deceleration, while Figure 6 shows the difference in deformation between a shell and a solid modelling.

Diameter - thickness (mm)	Shell elements		Solid elements	
	Crushing stroke (mm)	Average deceleration (g)	Crushing stroke (mm)	Average deceleration (g)
80 - 2.5	36	15	37	16
80 - 2	48	13	42	15
80 - 1.5	86	7	83	8
50 - 2.5	52	14	53	13
50 - 2	83	8	85	7
50 - 1.5	130	5	125	6

Table 2. Numerical results using shell and solid elements

Fig. 6. Difference in deformation for a) shell and b) solid elements

For the impact attenuator the same procedure that was used for cylindrical tubes has been followed.

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL DYNAMIC ANALYSIS FOR A CFRP FORMULA SAE IMPACT ATTENUATOR

The “rigid wall planar moving forces” card has been implemented with a mass of 300 kg. This is modelling the obstacle that is impacting the attenuator with an initial velocity of 7 m/s. The support of the attenuator is modelled as “rigid wall planar”, with prescribed friction coefficient equal to 0.4.

Material type MAT_54 was used with Chang-Chang failure criteria. To avoid ductile behaviour with folding, it is important to change the element strength at some point of the collapse evolution. This is obtained thanks to a time-step failure parameter (TFAIL), which defines a limit to the element effective strain. This allows to reproduce the brittle behaviour of the material and, at the same time, to control the time-step value and therefore to reduce the analysis CPU time. After sensitivity analyses a TFAIL parameter equal to 0.8 was chosen for most of the herein performed calculations.

4 Experimental dynamic tests

All the dynamic experimental tests reported in this paper were performed at the Picchio S.p.A. plant in Ancarano (Italy) using a drop weight test machine with a 6 m free-fall height and a maximum mass of 413 kg.

For the experimental tests on cylindrical tubes was used an impact mass of 294 kg and an initial velocity of about 4 m/s. During the tests every tubes was supported at the bottom edge on a metallic base with air holes. The acceleration of the mass and the velocity at impact were measured using an accelerometer with 500g full-scale and a photocell, respectively. The most important parameters for crash resistance characterisation were computed and reported in detail in reference [10]. The tested CFRP tubes have absorbed impact energy by a progressive crushing process with two different deformation modes: splaying with axial splitting and fragmentation with debris. In all configurations, the residual part of the tubes results perfectly integer.

The frontal impact attenuator, also, was tested in dynamic compression using the same test instrumentation, but with different impact energy: 300 kg for the mass and 7 m/s for the initial velocity.

Fig. 7. Typical examples of progressive crush failure: (a) splaying with axial splitting; (b) fragmentation with debris

Performing the dynamic impact test, it is noticed that the manufacturing process of the composite impact attenuator has a significant influence on structural crashworthiness. In particular, the impacted sacrificial structure has a brittle failure up to some point, after which the detachment of the fabric laminates exactly along the bonding line of two parts of impact attenuator is predominant. This causes the decrement of the attenuator’s strength and stability and the failure of the structure, which was not able to show the expected resistance and crash impact behaviour.

In Figure 8(a) the nose cone fragments after the dynamic impact are shown. It is well visible that almost half of the attenuator material remained undamaged, i.e. the energy absorption results to be lower than what would be possible on the basis of the material amount and specific structure design. In Figure 8(b) it is possible to see the non-tested nose cone and the pieces of crashed attenuator positioned on it. This allows us to see the laminate breakage along the bonding line.

Fig. 8. Dynamic crash test: attenuator fragments after the crash (a) and laminate detachment zone (b)

In order to improve crush properties of the impact attenuator, a different manufacturing process, that take into consideration the positioning of the overlapping laminates respect to corner edges, was implemented, as described in section 2. In Figure 9 the fragments of an impact attenuator manufactured according to this second procedure are shown after the impact test. It is possible to see that previously resulting failure along connection of laminates is no more present and the overall structural behaviour is improved.

Fig. 9. Crashed impact attenuator after the improvement of manufacturing process

Fig. 10. Comparison of deceleration vs. time for two attenuators with the same geometry

Three impact attenuators were tested and results are reported in Figure 10 in terms of deceleration curves. Test 1 refers to the first manufactured attenuator batch without improvement of the lamination process. Test 2 and Test 3 refer to the second attenuator batch with the same geometry but with improvement of lamination process. As it can be noted, the change in the lamination process contributes significantly to the ability of the composite attenuator to absorb impact energy.

5 Comparison between numerical and experimental results

Table 3 summarizes the difference in percentage between the numerical and experimental results for the cylindrical tubes both for shell and solid model. Despite the numerical simplification, both the modelling techniques are able to reproduce quite closely the main crash parameters, in particular the total crushing stroke and the average deceleration. As mentioned before, the use of solids with interposition of one cohesive element layer allows also to view the delamination process with fronding, as it occurs in the experimental reality. The differences between numerical data and experimental ones are mainly due to the difficulty in simulating the initialization of the fragmentation phase and in taking into account the manufacturing defects of the tubes.

Specimen	Crush stroke error in %		Mean deceleration error in %	
	Shell	Solid	Shell	Solid
1	2.8	5.7	7.3	1.1
2	9.1	4.5	10.4	3.4
3	1.2	2.4	7.3	5.9
4	3.7	1.8	11.2	3.2
5	3.8	6.2	5.4	17.2
6	2.4	1.6	2.7	16.7

Table 3. Error in percentage between numerical and experimental data

In Figure 11 it is possible to see the comparison of deceleration vs. time curves of experimental test done on the Test 3 impact attenuator and numerical results obtained by LS-DYNA simulation. Beside the first peak (which is mostly due to numerical problems [17]) it can be noticed the similar trend of two curves. Average values of the deceleration are very close to 20 g, which is the main limitation

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL DYNAMIC ANALYSIS FOR A CFRP FORMULA SAE IMPACT ATTENUATOR

imposed by Formula SAE rules [15]. Further, as already pointed out in previously published works [10,14], the deceleration diagram is rather flat, approaching a ideal energy absorber behaviour.

Fig. 11. Comparison of experimental and numerical deceleration vs. time curves

In Figure 12 the comparison of force versus displacement curves is presented, obtained by experimental dynamic tests and crash dynamic numerical simulations carried out by LS-DYNA code. As mentioned before, the first critical peak is mostly a numerical problem as it does not appear in the experimental results. The trend of curves is almost the same. A nearly flat diagram of the impact force is obtained.

Fig. 12. Comparison of experimental and numerical force vs. displacement curves

In Figure 13(a) it is possible to see the flexural behaviour in the wall of the composite impact attenuator, subjected to dynamic loading conditions. In particular, this behaviour is well visible after the displacement of 100 mm, which corresponds to the half of the attenuator length. Results obtained by numerical simulations performed with the use of LS-DYNA explicit code, are shown in Figure 13(b). It is possible to notice that the flexion of the wall after the displacement of 100 mm during dynamic is confirmed also by simulations.

Fig. 13. Flexion of the attenuator wall subjected to dynamic compression test - comparison of experimental (a) and numerical (b) results

6 Conclusions

Development of a thin-walled CFRP impact attenuator for a Formula SAE racing car has been discussed in detail from a numerical and experimental point of view.

In order to set the appropriate values of the numerical LS-DYNA models, composite material characterisation tests and cylindrical tube crushing experiments were performed. The dynamic crash-tests were performed using a drop test machine, measuring the deceleration-time diagram and after integration processes load-shortening trend and energy absorbed by the structure. Despite the complexity of the fracture phenomenon, a good agreement between results has been achieved for simple tubular structures, using both shell and solid elements configuration.

Solid element model with interposition of one cohesive element layer confirms to be able to describe the fronding phenomenon, provided that proper cohesive data are supplied.

After the validation of the methodology for simple structures, analysis has moved to model a more complex geometry as the frontal impact attenuator for Formula SAE racing car. Performed experimental tests confirmed stable behaviour of the sacrificial structure with rather flat, almost constant force versus displacement curves and acceleration limit close to 20g. This value fits well with the requirements of SAE 2008 rules, as they require that the adopted solution leads to an average deceleration lower than 0.2 m/ms^2 (20g).

Furthermore, the explicit FE solver LS-DYNA has been able to predict experimental results regarding both resisting force and progressive collapse mechanism of the impact attenuator. Beside the

appropriate choice of trigger mechanism, the failure criteria was the most important parameter of the modeling of composite structure in order to predict brittle collapse of the nose cone. Force versus displacement diagram confirms that experimental and numerical results are almost the same.

7 Acknowledgements

The financial support from the Politecnico–FIAT partnership agreement, car body lightweight design theme, is gratefully acknowledged.

The availability of Picchio drop tower used for the experimental tests is gratefully acknowledged as well.

8 References

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